

Influence of national service training program in the lives of Dominican students

Jeric N. Atillano, Philip C. Cuizon, Randolph A. Gavina, Melanie D. Solis, Catherine R. Copia

Abstract

This study aimed to assess the influence of National Service Training Program in the lives of Dominican students. The participants include 104 enrolled students in the National Service Training Program (NSTP) across all courses in St. Dominic College of Asia during the academic year 2021-2022. The researchers developed a 20-item 5-Point Likert scale that measures the influence of NSTP programs in the lives of Dominican students. The self-made instrument underwent validation and reliability scoring and it was converted to online Google survey form. According to the results, National Service Training Programs positively influence the lives of Dominican students. For them, attending NSTP classes reminds them about their social responsibility, being positive amidst adversities, giving importance to community projects, enhanced critical thinking skills and the important roles Dominican students play in the society.

Keywords: Influence; National Service Training Program; Dominican students.

Jeric N. Atillano*

Philip C. Cuizon

Randolf A. Gavina

Melanie D. Solis

Catherine R. Copia

School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author's email address:

jericn_atillano@sdca.edu.ph

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Introduction

Filipino college students, especially lower year levels, are required to take units of National Service Training Program (NSTP) and Physical education as part of their curriculum regardless of their enrolled program. According to Laird et al. (2009), general courses are seen to be a factor in developing intellectual skills, personal and social responsibility of students. NSTP and physical education courses are found to be integral in the students' awareness, consciousness and social well-being. Individuals may participate in community service to look good in front of other people or to fulfill a requirement. But there are a lot of people who participate in community services, because it makes them happy and relieves their stress. Many have reported feeling as though they were contributing back to society (Berger & Milem, 2002 as cited in Dunn, 2018).

Methods

This study used a descriptive type of research with a quantitative approach. Descriptive research design is a type of research design that aims to obtain information to systematically describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. Quantitative approach means data are numerically represented. The researchers developed a 20-item 5-Point Likert scale that measures the influence of NSTP programs in the lives of Dominican students. The self-made instrument underwent validation and reliability scoring and it was converted to online Google survey form so that there is an increased participation coming from students. Data were collected electronically and statistically analyzed using SPSS.

Results and Analysis

Table 1 shows the profiling of respondents. For sex demographic profile, out of 104 respondents, 13 or 12 percent of the respondents are males, and 91 or 88 percent of the respondents are females. For school, 19 or 18 percent are respondents from School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, 19 or 18 percent are respondents from School of Business and Computer Studies, 55 or 53 percent are respondents from School of Health Science Profession, and 11 or 11 percent are respondents from School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management.

For courses, five (5) or 5 percent of the respondents are students from BA Multimedia Arts, seven (7) or 7 percent of the respondents are students from BS Accountancy, seven (7) or 7 percent of the respondents are students from BS Business Administration, 10 or 10 percent of the respondents are students from BS Hospitality Management, three (3) or 3 percent of the respondents are students from BS Information Technology, 24 or 23 percent of the respondents are students from BS Medical Technology, 29 or 28 percent of the respondents are students from BS Nursing, one (1) or 1 percent of the respondents are students from BS Pharmacy, one (1) or 1 percent of the respondents are students from BS Radiologic Technology, and one (1) or 1 percent of the respondents are students from Education.

Table 1
 Demographic profile of respondents (n=104)

Demographic Profile		n	%
Sex	Male	13	12
	Female	91	88
School	School of Arts, Sciences, and Education	19	18
	School of Business and Computer Studies	19	18
	School of Health Science Profession	55	53
	School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management	11	11
Courses	BA Multimedia Arts	5	5
	BS Accountancy	7	7
	BS Business Administration	7	7
	BS Hospitality Management	10	10
	BS Information Technology	3	3
	BS Medical Technology	24	23
	BS Nursing	29	28
	BS Pharmacy	1	1
	BS Psychology	14	13
	BS Radiologic Technology	2	2
	Education	2	2

Table 2 shows the summary of responses per statement. The statement that got the highest ‘Strongly Agree’ response is statement no. 1 “Attending NSTP Classes made me realize about taking responsibility in all my actions and behaviors in the community.”

This is followed with statement no. 5 “Attending NSTP classes helped me clearly understand the important roles I play in the society,” and statement no. 16 which is “Attending NSTP classes gave me a better understanding on how to become a better Filipino citizen”.

Table 2
 Summary of responses

Statement	SD	D	N	A	SA
1. Attending NSTP classes made me realize about taking responsibility in all my actions and behaviors in the community.			3	46	55
2. Attending NSTP classes made me an optimistic person regardless of the adversities.			15	49	40
3. Attending NSTP classes increased my desire to initiate projects for my community.			20	41	43
4. Attending NSTP classes enhanced my critical thinking skills.			12	50	42
5. Attending NSTP classes helped me clearly understand the important roles I play in society.			2	48	54
6. Attending NSTP classes increased my confidence in terms of community membership/participation.	1		18	47	38
7. Attending NSTP classes strengthened my convictions and personal views about social issues.			6	50	48
8. Attending NSTP classes helped me in developing a self-directed learning attitude	1		11	48	44
9. Attending NSTP classes aided me to become a good member in the community			11	43	50
10. Attending NSTP classes helped me in doing effective decisions	2		9	52	41
11. Attending NSTP classes helped me to become sensitive about relevant societal issues and trends	1		10	41	52
12. Attending NSTP classes inspired me to become an effective leader someday	4		20	42	38
13. Attending NSTP classes transformed me to become better Dominican student			8	55	41
14. Attending NSTP classes inspired me to become a proactive member in the society	1		13	51	39

15. Attending NSTP classes gave me an opportunity to collaborate with others in developing projects for the community.	3	18	44	39
16. Attending NSTP classes gave me a better understanding on how to become a better Filipino citizen.		6	45	53
17. Attending NSTP classes supported my advocacy to be a Filipino Patriot.	1	14	49	40
18. Attending NSTP classes helped me discover my potential in doing things for the society as a Filipino citizen.		5	58	41
19. Attending NSTP classes made me a person for others with social transformation.	2	16	51	35
20. Attending NSTP classes created a meaningful experience as a person with social responsibility.	1	5	55	43

Legend: SA= Strongly Agree; A=Agree; N=Neutral; D=Disagree; SD= Strongly Disagree

Table 3 shows the mean score for extent of influences of NSTP program per demographic profile. For sex demographic profile, male respondents obtained a mean score of 3.88 with a standard deviation of 0.50 which is verbally described as "Agree" and verbal interpreted as "High Influence", while female respondents obtained a mean score of 4.36 with a standard deviation of 0.51, which is verbally described as "Agree" and verbal interpreted as "Very High Influence".

For school demographic profile, respondents from School of Arts, Sciences, and Education obtained a mean score of 4.11 with a standard deviation of 0.46, which is verbally described as "Agree" and verbally interpreted as "High Influence"; respondents from School of Business and Computer Studies obtained a mean score of 4.53 with a standard deviation of 0.47 which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" and verbally interpreted as "Very High Influence".

Respondents from School of Health Science Profession obtained a mean score of 4.29 with a standard deviation of 0.51 which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" and verbally interpreted as "Very High Influence", and respondents from School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management obtained a mean score of 4.26 with a standard deviation of 0.70 which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" and verbally interpreted as "Very High Influence".

The overall level of extent of influence of NSTP in the lives of selected Dominican students is 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.53, which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" and verbally interpreted as "Very High Influence".

Table 3
Mean score for extent of influences of NSTP Program per demographic profile

Demographic Profile		Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	3.88	0.50	Agree	High Influence
	Female	4.36	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
	Total	4.30	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
School	School of Arts, Sciences, and Education	4.11	0.46	Agree	High Influence
	School of Business and Computer Studies	4.53	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
	School of Health Science Profession	4.29	0.51	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
	School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management	4.26	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
	Total	4.30	0.53	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/Very High; 3.40-4.19= Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Average; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table 4 shows the test for significant difference per demographic profile. For Sex at birth demographic profile, the computed p-value is 0.005 which is less than .05 alpha level, this would mean that there is significant difference and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, female respondents perceived a more positive influence of the NSTP program in their lives compared with male respondents.

For school demographic profile, the computed p-value is 0.104 which is greater than .05 alpha level, this would mean that there is no significant difference and null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the difference in mean score on the extent of influence of NSTP is not significantly different.

Table 4
Test for significant difference

Demographic Profile	P-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Sex at Birth	0.005	Significant	Reject
School	0.104	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Discussion

National Service Training Programs positively influence the lives of Dominican students. For them attending NSTP classes reminds them about their social responsibility, being positive amidst adversities, increasing importance of community projects, enhanced critical thinking skills and the important role those Dominican students play in the society. NSTP Program also increases community membership, self-directed attitudes and initiatives, effective decision making, social sensitivity with current issues, and becoming a leader in the future. Attending NSTP classes increase group dynamics, task collaboration, making a better view of what Filipino citizenship is, increase support in terms of indigenous advocacy and self-discovery with one potential in providing solutions to the community.

Overall, the NSTP classes positively influence the life of Dominican Students. It is very important that our students have this positive attitude towards life and its adversities. The NSTP program increases the importance of being a Filipino with responsibility and social sensitivity on societal issues. This study also concluded that women should play an active role toward patriotism and community development.

Recommendation

The researchers recommend research enthusiast to explore more about how National Service Training Program can influence more the lives of the students through in-depth study or qualitative in nature. They can also explore relative variables related to the conduct of this study for future research replications.

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